

XROTOR

X-shaped Radical Offshore Wind Turbine for Overall Cost of Energy Reduction

D6.1

O&M Costs for the X-Rotor Modelled

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About X-ROTOR

X-ROTOR: “X-shaped Radical Offshore wind Turbine for Overall cost of energy Reduction” is a Horizon 2020 funded project which aims to develop a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept.

The X-ROTOR project is led by University of Strathclyde (UK) in partnership with Norwegian University of Science and Technology (Norway), Delft University of Technology (Netherlands), University College Cork (Ireland), Fundacion Cener National Renewable Energy Centre (Spain) and GE Renovables España (Spain).

As the effects of climate change are becoming ever more visible, Europe has raised its target for the amount of energy it consumes from renewable sources from the previous goal of 27% to 32% by 2030. Offshore wind energy can play a key role in achieving the EU target and contribute to the required 40% reduction in CO₂ emissions. However, to achieve the previously mentioned targets the cost of offshore wind must be reduced. The X-ROTOR concept provides a direct route to drastically reducing both capital and operating costs of energy from offshore wind.

The project runs for three years from January 2021, during which time, the concept will be developed through a holistic consideration of technical, cost, environmental and socio-economic impact aspects.

If proven feasible, X-ROTOR will, as a disruptive new offshore wind turbine concept, create new opportunities for the European wind energy industry and play an important role maintaining the EU’s position as global technological leader in renewable energy, reducing greenhouse gas emissions and decarbonising the EU economy.

For more information see <https://xrotor-project.eu>

Description of the deliverable and its purpose

Deliverable 6.1: “O&M costs for the X-rotor modelled” is concerned with estimating the operational expenditure for the X-rotor concept. The objective is to model the X-rotor O&M costs under several modelling assumptions. Estimates of O&M costs will then be incorporated into the over-arching aim of work package 6 – namely to determine the cost of energy for the X-rotor concept and compare with traditional wind turbine concepts. One of the key selling points of the X-rotor concept is a reduction of O&M costs. Modelling O&M costs therefore plays an important role in providing a business case for the X-rotor.

An existing validated O&M cost model developed at the university of Strathclyde is used for estimating O&M costs. The challenge of the deliverable lies in capturing the impact of the X-rotor’s unique characteristics on operations at an offshore site, and capturing that impact via alterations to the existing model. There are significant uncertainties surrounding failure modes for novel wind turbine concepts which should be explored. On top of this, there are uncertainties associated with the operational strategy of the X-Rotor which should also be explored. Throughout this work the researchers have adopted a conservative approach; over-estimating any uncertain inputs or model adjustments to produce “worst case scenario” results.

This report details the methodology employed to estimate the O&M costs for the X-rotor. It goes on to define a baseline comparison to existing turbine concepts, the purpose of which is to investigate the assumption of lower O&M costs for the X-rotor. The sensitivity of results to modelling assumptions are then explored via a series of sensitivity analyses.

List of acronyms

O&M	Operation and Maintenance
LCoE	Levelised Costs of Energy
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
WP	Work Package
XRC	X-ROTOR concept
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OWF	Offshore Wind Farm
WT	Wind Turbine
HAWT	Horizontal-Axis Wind Turbine
CAPEX	Capital Expenditure
VAWT	Veritcal-Axis Wind Turbine
mr	Minor Repair
Mr	Major Repair
MR	Major Replacement

1 Introduction

This report supports deliverable D6.1: modelling Operations & Maintenance (O&M) costs for the X-Rotor concept. It describes the methodology used for modelling O&M costs for the XRC and compares the resultant O&M costs to conventional turbine concepts. Sensitivity analyses of key modelling assumptions are also presented.

The document is organised as follows: Section 2 summarises the cost reduction opportunities for the XRC. Section 3 discusses the influential parameters for cost modellers & how they change for XRC O&M cost modelling. Section 4 gives an overview of the O&M cost model used and the alterations made for XRC O&M cost modelling. Section 5 presents a baseline study comparing the XRC to existing turbine concepts. Section 6 presents sensitivity analyses on baseline assumptions. Section 7 summarises future work and section 8 summarises the key conclusions of the report.

2 O&M Cost Reduction Opportunities for the XRC

The O&M costs of existing offshore wind farms make up approximately 30% of the Levelised Cost of Energy (LCoE) (Carroll, et al., 2017). The X-Rotor Concept (XRC) presents a potential to reduce O&M costs for several reasons. The most significant, and immediate, reductions are twofold (Leithead *et al.*, 2019):

1. The X-Rotor does not have either a gearbox or a multi-pole generator. These are two of the components that contribute most to downtime for offshore turbines (Carroll, et al., 2017; Pinar Pérez *et al.*, 2013).
2. The secondary Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines (HAWTs) can be designed such that they do not require a jack-up vessel upon failure of the drive train or hub. This can significantly reduce costs associated with Jack-Up Vessels (JUVs).

Additionally, (McMorland *et al.*, 2022) outline several more O&M cost reduction opportunities:

3. The power converter can be housed within a central module within the tower, improving accessibility by locating it far closer to sea level.
4. If one of the secondary HAWT power converters fail, the X-Rotor can be designed such that the remaining functional HAWT can still produce power by a control strategy based on the remaining power converter. This would provide a measure of redundancy unavailable to conventional turbines, making a batch repair strategy more feasible.
5. Modular design of secondary rotor drive trains would have a significant impact through the potential for simpler corrective maintenance. The effect is summarised in figure 1. Either the module could be replaced quickly offshore if a spare is available, or it could be removed and repaired onshore in the event a spare is not available. This presents an ideal scenario where both cost and safety are improved, as technicians would spend less time working offshore. The length of weather windows needed to perform many maintenance tasks would also be reduced, meaning that uncertainty in weather forecasts would have a diminished impact on operational risk.

3 Influential Cost Model Parameters & How they Change for the XRC

One of the purposes of this work package is to capture the advantages of the XRC outlined above. This requires altering some the assumptions which are made in O&M cost modelling of traditional HAWTs. Figure 2 summarises the factors that make up operational expenditure at offshore wind farms. Those aspects most likely to differ for the XRC compared to conventional HAWTs are highlighted. Note that some aspects are repeated under different cost headings, as they effect multiple categories. Some important considerations for the highlighted aspects are as follows – for a more detailed review of operations and maintenance modelling with considerations for novel wind turbine concepts, see (McMorland *et al.*, 2022).

Figure 1. Diagram of timeline for a repair task for an X-rotor turbine with a modular secondary rotor design (top); and without (bottom). The time estimations for each part are based on discussions with a commercial CTV charter company and other researchers. The repair times for minor/major/replacement are taken from Carroll et al. [3]. The “//” indicated the time axis is cut in this period. The yellow shaded areas indicated the time where the modular rotor will have influence on the repair time. Figure taken from (Flannigan *et al.*, 2022).

3.1 Failure Modelling

There are some challenges for modelling XRC failures. Firstly, there is very limited data for operational Vertical-Axis Wind Turbines (VAWTs), creating an attendant uncertainty for the components that make up the vertical-axis part of the turbine. The XRC does not have a power take-off system on the vertical axis but there is the main bearing, blades and loading implications on the tower to consider. The main bearing is a particularly troublesome component for conventional HAWTs, and the uncertainty associated with different loading behaviour for the XRC provides additional complications.

Secondary HAWT rotors can draw more directly on existing failure data for conventional HAWTs. The biggest discrepancy is in the different rotational speed of the XRC HAWTs. The rotational speed of these blades is much faster than conventional HAWTs. While the increased rotational speed provides an advantage in eliminating the need for a gearbox and multi-pole generator, the impact on remaining components is uncertain.

Figure 2. Breakdown of operations and maintenance costs for an offshore wind farm.

There are, however, also some potential advantages of modelling XRC reliability over traditional HAWTs. Firstly, the most extensive reliability analysis for conventional offshore turbines considers a dataset of 3MW machines (Carroll *et al.*, 2016). As the industry continues to roll out turbines of increasing power rating, the figures in this study become increasingly out of date. However, they are in line with the power rating of the smaller HAWTs used on the XRC. Also, given there are at least 2 secondary HAWTs on each X-rotor, the learning rate for reliability data will be at least twice as fast.

Failure rates present possibly the largest epistemic uncertainty in O&M cost modelling for the XRC. However, this does not necessarily constitute a major disadvantage over O&M cost modelling for traditional HAWTs. Failure data is generally hard to come by in the industry due to strict confidentiality practices put in place by Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs). While the change in topology for the XRC makes it difficult to predict failure rates accurately from existing data for HAWTs, the shift to larger turbines with medium speed and direct drive turbines can be seen as analogously challenging for HAWT O&M cost modelling.

This modelling uncertainty can be addressed in several ways. The first is to adopt a conservative approach for XRC failure modelling by assuming increased failure rates compared to traditional HAWTs. This doesn't address the uncertainty directly, but does explore a worse-than-expected scenario which is useful for making an economic argument for the XRC. Indeed, this is the approach taken in section 4.2. Sensitivity analysis of failure rates on modelling output is the second. The third is to use some form of expert judgement, as has been done previously by (Zitrou *et al.*, 2015) for quantifying risk from epistemic uncertainty on availability for offshore wind farms.

In the modelling carried out in this work, the XRC has a higher overall failure rate than conventional HAWTs, due to the conservative estimates mentioned above and an increase in the number of components. This will mean more frequent transfers to the XRC and may necessitate a bigger workforce. In reality, the XRC provides opportunities to decrease overall failure rate compared to conventional HAWTs. Staff costs might be reduced by using onshore technicians to repair spare modules. This would reduce the amount of training necessary for offshore work and working at height, increasing improving technician health and safety.

As summarised by figure 1, modular secondary HAWTs present a significant potential for reduction in replacement times. The extent of this reduction is another epistemic uncertainty, and similar steps to those outlined for failure rates as outlined in section 3.2.1 should be taken to explore any assumptions made. While

replacement times have the highest uncertainty, minor and major repair times might also differ from conventional turbines – albeit less substantially.

3.2 Repair & Vessel Strategy

Maintenance strategy can have a significant effect on O&M costs. Operators must balance additional vessel costs (via either purchasing or leasing) with lost revenue costs from turbine downtime if they are to successfully minimise O&M cost. While there are several tools in the literature dedicated to vessel fleet optimisation and repair strategy selection (Lazakis and Khan, 2021; Dalgic *et al.*, 2014; Superstad, et al., 2017), there are several characteristics of the XRC that might motivate an altered vessel purchase/hire strategy.

The XRC has more components than a conventional HAWTs. This might encourage the hiring or purchase of additional Crew Transfer Vessels (CTVs). However, it is anticipated that there would be a degree of over-engineering of some components to reduce their failure rate. While CTVs can tackle most repairs, they do not have enough deck space to accommodate a removed XRC HAWT module. Operators would need to hire or purchase more expensive vessels for this purpose. (McMorland *et al.*, 2022) suggest a Service Operations Vessel (SOV) would be suitable for the purpose, and (Flannigan *et al.*, 2022) propose Fast Supply Vessels (FSVs). Another option would be to not design modular secondary HAWTs, but to facilitate rapid removal and replacement of individual HAWT components. This would remove the need for additional deck space. Considerations for the hire of JUVs would almost certainly be different than conventional geared HAWTs, reducing costs considerably.

The uncertainty surrounding vessel requirements could be offset by the redundancy introduced by multiple secondary HAWT modules. This has the potential to reduce the focus on corrective maintenance actions and may encourage alternative maintenance strategies, as summarised by figure 3. As opposed to the ASAP approach (i.e. repairs are an immediate priority upon failure), maintenance strategies where repairs are undertaken after some pre-defined threshold become more appealing. This might take the form of a power threshold or a failure threshold – either for failures of the same type or failures in general. Most optimistic would be a “scheduled maintenance only” strategy, however this would likely be unfeasible unless there were more than two secondary HAWT modules.

Figure 3. Potential maintenance strategies for the XRC. Taken from (McMorland *et al.*, 2022)

4 Strathclyde O&M Cost Model

In this work package, all O&M cost modelling is performed using the StrathOW-OM model developed at the Centre for Doctoral Training in Wind Energy Systems. The model was initially developed to explore the use of heavy lift vessels for offshore wind farms between 2012 and 2013 (Dinwoodie *et al.*, 2013; Dinwoodie *et al.*, 2012). It was further developed to capture the full range of operations associated with offshore wind maintenance, and verified by comparison to other cost modelling tools (Dinwoodie *et al.*, 2015). Further examples of the model’s utility in academia are provided by (Dalgic *et al.*, 2015; Dalgic *et al.*, 2015) and (Carroll, et al., 2017).

Figure 4 presents a schematic of the model. It hinges on a central operational simulation, consisting of a series of shifts simulated in the time domain. First, several variables are calculated for the lifetime of the farm at an hourly resolution based on user inputs. Namely the important simulated variables are: a time-series of significant wave height and wind speed, the corresponding ideal power production for the farm, and the probability of a subsystem failure in each time-step. The weather conditions are generated using a correlated, Multivariate Auto-Regressive approach (MAR) (Hagen et al., 2013). A Non-Homogeneous Poisson Process (NHPP) is used in conjunction with a Power Law Process (PLP) to model reliability through time (Gao et al., 2009), or a Madsen and Stiesdal lifetime failure distribution which incorporates serial defects can be used in the model. The parameters of the failure model are user inputs. For each time step, the conditional reliability is compared to a randomly generated number to determine if a subsystem has failed. Ideal power production is derived from a user specified power curve, and depends on the simulated wind speed time-series.

The combined user inputs (namely climate time-series, vessel specification & fleet configuration, wind farm/turbine specification and cost variables) inform three simulations which feed into the central operational simulation (namely the synthetic climate time-series, accessibility and operability analysis and failure analysis). Separate functions are used to simulate minor and major repairs, which can be addressed by Crew Transfer Vessel (CTV), and major replacements, which are addressed by Jack-Up Vessel (JUV). Once the shift is simulated, the model records the condition of the wind farm in terms of turbines available and resources utilised. The process is repeated for the specified lifetime of the farm, and the lifetime power production and availability are calculated and stored. This is repeated until there is convergence of availability estimates on cross-simulation values.

Finally, cross-simulation calculations are passed to model outputs for post-processing. Outputs consist of a comprehensive list of Key Performance Indicators (availability, power production and number of failures), cost estimates (revenue, lost production costs, vessel and staff costs, costs of spare parts) and vessel specific information (CTV utilisation, number of JUV charters).

Figure 4. Overview of the StrathOW-OM model.

4.1 Changes to Model Functionality

New functionality has been added to the Operational Simulations block to account for altered maintenance practices for the XRC. Specifically, two new functions have been added to the simulation loop that perform module replacement and onshore repair of secondary HAWT modules. The new functions conform to the shift-based time-domain methodology used by StrathOW-OM and run alongside the existing operational functions for CTV and JUV repairs. They differ in that module replacements require vessels with adequate deck space and weight capacity to transport spare XRC modules to and from shore for repair. For this reason, Fast Supply Vessels (FSVs) are used for module replacements. Upon failure of a sub-assembly within a

secondary HAWT, replacement tasks are assigned to FSVs in the same way a minor repair is assigned to a CTV. The replacement is subject to restrictions on available weather windows, number of spare modules and the maximum module capacity of the vessel. Module replacements are non-cumulative, meaning that if a replacement can only be partially completed within any given shift, it will instead be delayed until the next available shift where it can be fully completed. The onshore repair function, however, is cumulative. Onshore repair jobs are therefore allowed to span multiple shifts. The onshore repairs function's job is to simulate the repair of modules onshore given user inputs of repair time and number of technicians required. There is also a slight alteration to allow for one of the secondary HAWTs to remain operational on a turbine where the other has failed. This consists of a clause to tell the simulations block that the turbine is effectively running at half capacity. A 5MW XRC is therefore effectively modelled as 2x2.5MW conventional HAWTs producing exactly half the power of a 5MW HAWT. This is another conservative assumption, as the control strategy of the X-Rotor is expected to provide closer to 60-70% of rated power when one secondary HAWT is operational.

4.2 Changes to Model Inputs

Inputs also require altering to reflect the characteristics of the XRC. The primary differences have to do with failure modes. Failure rates, repair times and costs of spare parts differ from traditional HAWTs. Firstly, failures are split into turbine modes and secondary-HAWT modes. Turbine modes are those which describe the vertical axis components – the top & bottom pairs of blades, pitch system, control system, safety systems, transformer, power converters and supply, service items, tower/foundations, pitch system, main bearing and some electrical systems. Secondary HAWT modes comprise of generator, HAWT rotor blades, sensors and HAWT rotor hubs.

In the baseline case outlined in this report, failure modes are based on existing failure data for conventional offshore HAWTs. (Carroll *et al.*, 2016) provide the most extensive reliability analysis for conventional offshore turbines, and therefore provide the basis upon which failure modes are derived here. Baseline failure rates are consistent with those used by (Flannigan *et al.*, 2022). Where component failure are estimated to be less frequent for the XRC than a conventional HAWT, the same failure rate is used for that component as in (Carroll *et al.*, 2016). As described in section 3, to ensure a conservative approach, when component failure rates are estimated to possibly be higher for the XRC, they are increased by 15%. In contrast to (Flannigan *et al.*, 2022), a main bearing failure rate is also introduced here for the vertical axis part of the turbine. To be conservative, main bearings are considered to fail more frequently in the XRC. (Hart, et al., 2019) estimate main bearing replacement rates at 0.015 per year for one configuration of turbine and 0.0075 for another. As a conservative estimate, the higher figure is used here. This is interpreted as a major replacement (MR) rate. Major replacements are assumed to be defined as in (Carroll *et al.*, 2016) – a repair costing more than €10,000. The number of minor (mr) and major (Mr) repairs are estimated by assuming a constant ratio of total failures to each failure category as that found in (Carroll *et al.*, 2016). The definition of mr and Mr repairs are also consistent with (Carroll *et al.*, 2016) – i.e. a minor repair is one costing less than €1,000 and a major repair is one costing between €1,000 and €10,000. Failure costs for the main bearing are assumed to be equivalent to the average failure cost for all components. Note that these failure rate figures are explored in subsequent sensitivity analyses.

Failure costs are estimated by first estimating the cost of the component for that particular concept and then maintaining equal ratios of component costs to mr/Mr/MR repairs. The cost of components are derived by the equations contained in (Fingersh, 2006). For turbine-level failures, components are assumed to be the same cost as a 5MW HAWT turbine. For secondary-rotor level failures, they are assumed to be the same cost as a 2.5MW HAWT turbine. Failure data contained in (Carroll *et al.*, 2016) is generalised to a 3MW turbine in order to derive component-to-repair cost ratios.

A summary of the failure mode input parameters used in the baseline scenario can be found in the appendix.

5 Baseline Case Study

The baseline case study consists of a wind farm of 100 XRCs located 100km from shore. OPEX costs are compared to a similar farm made up of existing WT concepts; namely a conventional 3-stage geared HAWT and a direct drive HAWT. The 3 scenarios are subject to the following assumptions.

1. The XRC has the following attributes.
 - a. Failure rates and costs are derived as outlined in section 4.2.
 - b. Secondary HAWTs are assumed to be modular. When a component in the secondary HAWT module fails, the module is removed by an FSV and subsequently repaired onshore.
 - c. When one of the secondary HAWTs fail, the XRC is assumed to operate at 50% capacity.
 - d. The hypothetical wind farm has 4 CTVs, 1 FSV and a pool of 30 technicians. JUVs are hired on a fix-on-fail basis for vertical axis component replacements.
2. The geared HAWT concept has:
 - a. Failure rates and costs consistent with (Carroll *et al.*, 2016), excluding the generator, which is assumed to fail with the frequency of a PMSG in (Carroll, et al., 2017).
 - b. 5CTVs, 30 technicians and JUVs are hired on a fix-on-fail basis.
3. For the direct drive concept:
 - a. For most of the components, failure rates and costs are consistent with (Carroll *et al.*, 2016). However, the generator and power converter failure modes are consistent with the those for direct drive machines found in (Carroll, et al., 2017).
 - b. A main bearing failure mode is also introduced. The same assumptions are used for deriving main bearing failure rates and costs for the XRC, outlined in section 4.2. The main bearing failure mode is introduced for the direct drive configuration as the main bearing failure rate is grouped with the gearbox failure rate in the previously used input data. When the gearbox is removed for the direct drive configuration the main bearing failure mode gets removed. Reintroducing it here eliminates the above issue.
 - c. There are 5CTVs, 30 technicians and JUVs are hired on a fix-on-fail basis.
4. In all scenarios:
 - a. JUV charters are 60 days long.
 - b. The same technician salaries, CTV characteristics, JUV costs and weather time-series are used, such that they are directly comparable.
 - c. The wind farm lifetime is 20 years.

5.1 Results

Key model outputs are shown in table 1. Despite having the highest failure rate due to conservative estimates for a “worst case scenario” approach, the XRC has a higher availability and lower lost revenue costs than both the geared and direct drive concepts. This can most reasonably be attributed to a reduction in major replacements requiring a JUV. Figure 5 confirms that transport costs are significantly lower for the XRC. It is worth noting that even in a conservative estimate, the XRC has a lower cost (in terms of O&M costs) than the currently predominant WT technologies.

	Geared HAWT	Direct Drive	XRC
Availability (%)	89.70	89.93	90.89
Lost Revenue (€m)	243	239	212
λ (fail/turb/year)	6.21	6.25	7.46
Jack-Up Required Failures	135	56	42

Table 1: Comparison of key model outputs for the baseline XRC concept, geared HAWT concept and direct drive turbines over a 20-year lifespan.

Figure 5 shows reduced costs associated with the XRC in terms of lost production, transport, staff and repairs.

Savings in lost revenue can be attributed not only to fewer JUV failures, but also to the ability of the XRC to operate at reduced capacity when one of the secondary HAWTs fails. Note that this assumption is explored further in section 6.2. The most significant savings from the Geared HAWT are due to reductions in vessel costs. Where geared HAWT turbines require JUVs for gearbox, generator, main bearing, pitch system, hub and blade replacements, the XRC reduces JUV failure modes to just the primary axis blades, hub, pitch system and the main bearing. There is far less saving in transport costs compared to the direct drive concept – for both the XRC and direct drive concepts, the main bearing is the dominant driver of JUV costs. Given the high costs associated JUV mobilisation and hire, reduced JUV usage presents an opportunity for significant O&M cost reduction. Staff and repair costs also see reductions, albeit less significant. Reduced staff costs result from a smaller pool of offshore technicians for the XRC, as modular secondary HAWTs allow maintenance to be conducted onshore. Onshore technicians are assumed to be paid less than offshore. Reduced repair costs can be attributed to smaller components, which are generally cheaper to repair or replace. In relative terms, the O&M costs for direct drive turbines are 11% higher than the XRC. Comparing the O&M cost categories between XRC and direct drive turbines: lost production costs are 16% higher, transport costs 7% higher, staff costs 5% higher and repair costs 28% higher. Overall O&M costs for Geared HAWT turbines are 30% higher. Comparing the O&M cost categories between XRC and geared turbines: lost production costs are 17% higher, transport costs 32% higher, staff costs 5% higher and repair costs 174% higher. The cost delta between the XRC and traditional turbines is expected to increase in the X-Rotor’s favour.

Figure 5. Comparison of OPEX costs for the XRC, direct drive and geared-HAWT concepts.

6 Sensitivity Analyses

This section presents three sensitivity analyses of the assumptions made in the baseline case study. Namely: the overall failure rate of the XRC (section 6.1), the failure rate of the main bearing (section 6.2), and the assumption that the turbine operates at half capacity when one secondary HAWT fails (section 6.3).

6.1 Overall Failure Rate

Failure rates are a significant uncertainty for wind farm OPEX modellers. The problem is exacerbated when modelling the XRC because it is a novel device with no historic failure data. A sensitivity analysis of the failure rate assumptions made in section 5 is a simple yet useful method of addressing this uncertainty. Here, the failure rates are varied from the baseline assumption of 1.15 times the corresponding failure rate in (Carroll

et al., 2016) – henceforth this will be referred to as the failure rate factor. Scenarios from 0.9 to 1.3 times Carroll *et al.*'s component failure rates are explored in 0.05 increments. Note that only the components which are assumed to fail more often for the XRC are affected by the failure rate factor.

Figure 6 shows how (a) the availability and (b) the O&M cost varies with the overall failure rates. As a reference point, the geared and direct drive baseline estimates are also shown. If failure rates are the same as conventional HAWTs, there is a significant increase in availability for the XRC. Correspondingly, O&M costs are far lower. Availability remains higher, and O&M costs lower, up until beyond a failure rate factor of 1.2. Note, however, that increased failure rates for the XRC is a conservative assumption. It is commonly assumed that smaller components have smaller failure rates. Indeed, the older wind turbine reliability initiatives tend to have smaller failure rates than more modern studies (Pfaffel *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 6. Sensitivity of XRC (a) availability and (b) O&M cost to failure rate assumptions. Failure rates for components that assumed to fail more often on the XRC are varied from 0.9 to 1.3 times that found in (Carroll *et al.*, 2016).

6.2 Main Bearing Failure Rate

Of the 42 JUV failures associated with the XRC presented in the baseline case, 36 were due to main bearing replacements. Main bearing failures therefore account for 85% of JUV use and remain a significant cost factor for the XRC. What's more, the main bearing presents a particular uncertainty within XRC O&M cost modelling for two reasons:

1. As noted by (Hart, et al., 2019), main bearing failures are either neglected as a category or lumped in with other components in many prominent and often-cited WT reliability analyses – e.g. (Carroll *et al.*, 2016; Wilkinson *et al.* 2011; Spinato *et al.*, 2009). Reliability figures are therefore only based on one study (Hart, et al., 2019), and only replacement rates are presented there.
2. XRC main bearings are in the vertical-axis primary turbine. Their operating conditions and the loads they are subject to differ from conventional HAWT turbines, as might their geometry and weight. Their failure behaviour might therefore differ significantly from those available in the literature.

The O&M costs (and the attendant uncertainty in the O&M costs) associated with main bearings would be significantly reduced if the need for JUVs was removed. However, any reduction in O&M costs would at least partially be negated by an increased Capital Expenditure (CAPEX), as it would require some removal mechanism for the main bearing which would incur a capital cost. An analysis on the sensitivity of O&M costs to main bearing failure rate would therefore be beneficial to the design process of the XRC.

The sensitivity analysis is undertaken by varying the main bearing failure rate from 0% of the cited figure of 0.015 to 250% of that figure. O&M costs for the various main bearing failure rate scenarios are compared to the ‘established X-rotor’ scenario explored by (Flannigan *et al.*, 2022). Since (Flannigan *et al.*, 2022) do not include a main bearing failure rate in their OPEX modelling, they provide a useful measure against which the sensitivity of main bearing failures can be explored. Figure 7 (a) shows the added O&M costs per turbine due to the inclusion of a main bearing failure rate on top of the assumptions of (Flannigan *et al.*, 2022). If XRC main bearings were to fail as frequently as conventional HAWTs, there is an additional O&M cost of approximately €1M per turbine. The reason is that main bearings would become the predominant JUV replacement failure mode. Where (Flannigan *et al.*, 2022) estimate JUV required failures to total 6 over the farm’s lifetime for the rest of the components, the number would increase to 42 for the baseline case study explored in this report. Figure 7 (b) explores the relationship between main bearing failure rate and JUV costs. Where repair costs due to main bearing failures are unavoidable regardless of the existence of a removal mechanism and some lost productions costs would remain, most of the vessel costs could be eliminated. Unlike the plot of 7 (a), the relationship of 7 (b) is not linear. Rather, as more JUV failures occur, the more can be replaced within the same JUV charter.

Based on figures 7 (a) and (b), cost savings of between €519,000 and €975,000 per turbine could be achieved through an inbuilt main bearing removal mechanism if main bearing failure rates were equal to conventional HAWT turbines. Increasing the XRC main bearing failure rate to 150% of conventional HAWT turbines increases potential savings to between €722,000 and €1,457,000 per turbine. At 200%, the potential savings reach between €835,000 and €1,874,000 per turbine. At 250%, potential savings reach between €966,000 and €2,373,000 per turbine. If main bearing failure rates are decreased to 80% of estimates for conventional HAWTs cost savings of between €855,000 and €439,000 per turbine could be achieved. At an optimistic 50% reduction in failure rates, potential cost savings are between €512,000 and €290,000 per turbine.

6.3 Secondary HAWT Operation

The second XRC-specific sensitivity study explores the baseline assumption that, when one of the secondary HAWTs fails, the other remains operational. (Flannigan *et al.*, 2022) stress that this is a significant factor in lowering the XRCs O&M costs, as it significantly reduces lost production costs. They highlight that their established X-rotor (which has the same assumptions as the baseline scenario minus a main bearing failure rate)_model has approximately 1% higher availability than the primitive X-rotor (which assumes full turbine unavailability upon secondary HAWT failure) and direct-drive scenarios. Their primitive X-rotor scenario includes additional assumptions, namely:

1. Secondary HAWTs are not modular.
2. Secondary HAWT generator replacements require JUVs.

Here, these assumptions are disregarded. The baseline scenario, where a failure in one of the HAWTs reduces turbine capacity to 50%, is compared to a scenario where a failure of one HAWT renders the entire turbine unavailable. This way, the effect of the baseline assumption can be explored directly.

The effect of disregarding this assumption is shown in figure 8. Having full turbine unavailability from a failure of one HAWT component adds 0.95 €/MWh on to the total O&M cost, all of which is attributable to extra lost production costs. This is due to a 1.3% drop in availability, which results in a €38M drop in revenue. However, the 'XRC – Full Turbine Unavailable' scenario is still significantly cheaper than geared HAWT concept, and slightly cheaper than the direct drive concept.

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Added (a) O&M costs and (b) JUV costs per turbine compared to (Flannigan *et al.*, 2022), for different main bearing failure rate assumptions.

Figure 8. Comparison of baseline case study (in blue) to the scenario where a failure of one secondary HAWT leads to full turbine unavailability (red).

7 Future Work

Future work for the work package involves three aspects:

1. Further sensitivity analyses. There are several factors which might have a significant impact on XRC OPEX estimates. Namely:
 - a. Distance to shore. As shown by (Carroll, et al., 2017), OWFs with conventional turbines have a significant drop of availability when moving from 80-100km offshore when there is no change in the number of CTVs. If the XRC is not subject to a similar drop, the baseline case of section 5 could present a favorable picture of the XRC.
 - b. Power rating. The potential for upscaling of the XRC has not been explored. Where conventional turbines obtain a higher power rating by increasing the size of components, the XRC does so by adding more secondary HAWT models. This would provide additional redundancy at the cost of higher failure rates compared to the baseline XRC. However, failure rates for upscaled traditional HAWTs would also increase.
 - c. Failure rates of secondary HAWT modules. Like the sensitivity analyses of sections 6.2 and 6.3, failure rates of secondary HAWT modules are a unique consideration for the XRC. Their increased rotor speed and reduced blade length complicates failure modelling.
 - d. Vessel & repair strategies. As summarised in section 3.2, the vessel and repair strategy might differ significantly for the XRC. Thus far, there has been no exploration of different repair strategies, though they could affect O&M costs significantly. For example, one possibility would be to exploit the reduced space requirements for spare parts to store them offshore, even on the turbines themselves.
2. Introducing the XRC power curve to model functionality. The power curve will differ from the assumed 2x2.5MW HAWTs assumed in the baseline case. This will require further alterations to the StrathOW-OM functionality.
3. Incorporating OPEX estimates into overall cost of energy modelling. Ultimately this is the goal of work package 6. Once an overall cost of energy estimate can be obtained for the XRC, it will be compared to conventional HAWTs.

8 Conclusions

This report presents the work so far undertaken on work package 6 of the X-rotor project. O&M cost modelling has been undertaken via an altered version of the StrathOW-OM tool. The changes consist of new model functionality and revised failure inputs. New model functionality consists of additions to the simulations block of StrathOW-OM which model secondary HAWT removal, repair and replacement via fast supply vessels. Revised failure inputs attempt to capture shorter component replacement times, altered failure rates and reduced repair costs for X-rotor components. A baseline case study is presented comparing the XRC to conventional HAWT turbine concepts – namely geared HAWT and direct drive. This consists of hypothetical OWFs 100km from shore with 100 turbines. Three sensitivity analyses are undertaken to assess the suitability of baseline modelling assumptions. These focus on overall failure rates of components, main bearing failure rate and the assumption that the turbine can keep operating at 50% capacity when one secondary HAWT module fails. The main findings were:

1. The baseline scenario results in an XRC concept with lower O&M costs than both geared and direct drive HAWT concepts. Direct drive turbines have 11% higher O&M costs and geared turbines 30% higher. This delta is considered a “worst case scenario” due to conservative inputs, the cost difference is expected to increase in favour of the XRC as uncertainty is removed from the model inputs.
2. XRC O&M costs overtakes direct drive HAWT O&M costs when failure rates of components are increased to over 125% that of conventional HAWTs.
3. If the XRC component failure rates are the same as conventional HAWTs, direct drive turbines have 27% higher O&M costs and geared turbines 49% higher O&M costs. It is expected that something close to this scenario can be achieved for the XRC. This expectation will be more concisely explored as uncertainties of input variables are reduced.
4. The main bearing accounts for approximately €1M of O&M costs per turbine over a 20-year lifetime. Approximately €0.5M of this is due to JUV costs.
5. The assumption that XRC turbines operate at half capacity when one secondary HAWT module fails reduces O&M costs by 8% compared to the scenario where there is full turbine unavailability. The full turbine unavailability scenario still has a lower O&M cost than both the geared and direct-drive concepts. However, it is anticipated that secondary HAWT modules will produce closer to 60-70% of rated power when operating alone. This needs to be explored.

Future work will involve further sensitivity analyses of key modelling assumptions and incorporating OPEX estimates into overall cost of energy calculations, additional alterations to the existing O&M cost model and incorporation of O&M cost modelling results into a wider cost of energy estimate.

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Appendix

Failure Mode Inputs

		Geared HAWT			DD HAWT			XRC			Notes
		mr	Mr	MR	mr	Mr	MR	mr	Mr	MR	
Pitch System	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.824	0.179	0.001	0.824	0.179	0.001	0.948	0.206	0.001	Increased pitch activity for the XRC and larger blade mass – increased failure rate & cost.
	Repair Cost (€)	463	4,189	30,867	463	4,189	30,867	1,054	9,538	70,218	
	Repair Time (hrs)	9	19	25	9	19	25	9	19	25	
Generator	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.437	0.024	0.007	0.546	0.03	0.009	0.874	0.048	0.014	Small, low torque XRC generator. Rapid replacement of XRC modules
	Repair Cost (€)	178	3,898	66,825	830	18,164	311,374	89	1,949	33,412	
	Repair Time (hrs)	7	24	81	8	22	81	8	2	2	
Gearbox	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.395	0.038	0.154	0	0	0	0	0	0	No gearbox for XRC. Gearbox failures assumed to include main bearings.
	Repair Cost (€)	237	4,732	435,329	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Repair Time (hrs)	8	22	231	8	22	231	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Main Bearing	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0	0	0	0.015	0.06	0.36	0.015	0.06	0.36	Geared HAWT main bearing included in gearbox. XRC higher failure rate to account for uncertainty.
	Repair Cost (€)	N/A	N/A	N/A	370	4,572	108,357	605	7,700	213,404	
	Repair Time (hrs)	N/A	N/A	N/A	7	17	116	7	17	116	
Blades (Primary turbine)	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.456	0.01	0.001	0.456	0.01	0.001	0.524	0.01	0.001	Larger XRC blades - blade failure rate scaled linearly with blade length.
	Repair Cost (€)	369	3,259	195,517	369	3,259	195,517	1,462	12,901	774,071	
	Repair Time (hrs)	9	21	288	9	21	288	9	21	288	
Blades (Secondary HAWT rotors)	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	0.775	0	0	Small & lights XRC blades, simple repair. Only blade replacements considered
	Repair Cost (€)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	241	N/A	N/A	
	Repair Time (hrs)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	2	0	0	
Grease/Oil/ Cooling liquid	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.407	0.006	0	0.407	0.006	0	0.814	0.012	0	Double failure rate for XRC for 2 PTOs. No gearbox, increased HAWT speed.
	Repair Cost (€)	257	3,217	N/A	257	3,217	N/A	160	2,000	N/A	
	Repair Time (hrs)	4	18	N/A	4	18	N/A	4	18	N/A	
Electrical Components	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.358	0.016	0.002	0.358	0.016	0.002	0.716	0.016	0.002	Double failure rate for XRC mr repairs for 2 PTOs. Mr & MR assumed to be out with secondary HAWTs.
	Repair Cost (€)	167	3,333	20,000	167	3,333	20,000	167	3,333	20,000	
	Repair Time (hrs)	5	14	18	5	14	18	5	14	18	
Controls	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.355	0.054	0.001	0.358	0.016	0.002	0.355	0.054	0.001	Same figures used for all concepts.
	Repair Cost (€)	200	2,000	13,000	200	2,000	13,000	200	2,000	13,000	
	Repair Time (hrs)	8	14	12	8	14	12	8	14	12	

		Geared HAWT			DD HAWT			XRC			Notes
		mr	Mr	MR	mr	Mr	MR	mr	Mr	MR	
Hub	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.182	0.038	0.001	0.182	0.038	0.001	0.182	0.038	0.001	Slightly larger hub for XRC.
	Repair Cost (€)	220	2,065	130,797	220	2,065	130,797	437	4,095	259,320	
	Repair Time (hrs)	10	40	298	10	40	298	10	40	298	
Safety	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.373	0.004	0	0.373	0.004	0	0.373	0.004	0	Same figures used for all concepts.
	Repair Cost (€)	130	2,400	N/A	130	2,400	N/A	130	2,400	N/A	
	Repair Time (hrs)	2	7	N/A	2	7	N/A	2	7	N/A	
Sensors	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.247	0.07	0	0.247	0.07	0	0.247	0.07	0	Same figures used for all concepts.
	Repair Cost (€)	150	2,500	N/A	150	2,500	N/A	150	2,500	N/A	
	Repair Time (hrs)	8	6	N/A	8	6	N/A	8	6	N/A	
Heaters/Coolers	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.19	0.007	0	0.19	0.007	0	0.19	0.007	0	Same figures used for all concepts. Smaller heaters/coolers necessary for XRC
	Repair Cost (€)	775	2,167	N/A	775	2,167	N/A	775	2,167	N/A	
	Repair Time (hrs)	5	14	N/A	5	14	N/A	5	14	N/A	
Yaw System	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.162	0.006	0.001	0.162	0.006	0.001	0	0	0	No yaw system in for the XRC
	Repair Cost (€)	319	6,828	248,451	319	6,828	248,451	N/A	N/A	N/A	
	Repair Time (hrs)	5	20	49	5	20	49	N/A	N/A	N/A	
Tower/Foundations	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.092	0.089	0	0.092	0.089	0	0.092	0.089	0	XRC tower holds less mass – cheaper repair costs than conventional HAWTS
	Repair Cost (€)	298	2,342	N/A	298	2,342	N/A	278	2,181	N/A	
	Repair Time (hrs)	5	2	N/A	5	2	N/A	5	2	N/A	
Power Supply/Converter	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.076	0.081	0.005	0.538	0.338	0.077	0.076	0.081	0.005	Higher frequency converter failure rate for direct drive machines. Assumed lower failure rate for XRC due to half-rated capacity.
	Repair Cost (€)	400	8,833	21,667	400	8,833	21,667	400	8,833	21,667	
	Repair Time (hrs)	7	14	57	7	14	57	7	14	57	
Service Items	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.108	0	0	0.108	0	0	0.108	0	0	Same figures used for all concepts.
	Repair Cost (€)	80	N/A	N/A	80	N/A	N/A	80	N/A	N/A	
	Repair Time (hrs)	7	N/A	N/A	7	N/A	N/A	7	N/A	N/A	
Transformer	Failure rate (fail/turb/year)	0.052	0.003	0.001	0.052	0.003	0.001	0.052	0.003	0.001	Same figures used for all concepts.
	Repair Cost (€)	182	4,417	134,437	182	4,417	134,437	182	4,417	134,437	
	Repair Time (hrs)	7	26	1	7	26	1	7	26	1	